

Construction Plans & BIMs / D4.2

WP 4, Task 4.2

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1. Introduction

As part of Task 4.2, **three BIM models** have been developed: one for the demo project in Barcelona and two for the demo in Brussels.

As in any building project, the main purpose of these digital models and plans is for the project architects to articulate **design proposals**, apply for a **building permit** and coordinate the **execution** of the construction works.

In the case of the Reconstruct demos, the main design goal for the architects was to demonstrate the **feasibility and viability** of the projects' **material innovations**, using components with a low-carbon composition and connections that enable disassembly and reuse. With these innovations, the Reconstruct partners aim to improve substantially on conventional construction practices in terms of **GHG emissions, resource use, and waste generation**, both on-site and at the end of the life cycle. The results of this design process are documented in D4.1 - Demo concepts & designs.

In this research project, the demo models are also given a second role, as they will be used to **iterate the digital tools of the Reconstruct ecosystem** - the digital product passports, the buildings material passports, the 6D-BIM modules and the Reconstruct interface linking them together in a comprehensive workflow.

Finally, the BIM models will be a means to **monitor and assess the material impacts** of the demos, both at the product and the building level, to report on the potential of the Reconstruct solutions.

Through these three approaches - material innovation, digital integration and impact assessment - the pilots will show different and complementary pathways to **a net-zero future for concrete** by 2050.

In this deliverable, D4.2, we will document the work that is completed in the first phase of Task 4.2: the **development of the BIM-models** themselves.

As a contribution to the **WP3 reports on the software tools**, planned for **May 2026**, M36 of the project, the partners of this task will then document the **co-creation activities with the focus group** and compile the results. These activities can only start once the local clusters are established and the assumptions for the digital tools are clear. Therefore, Task 4.2 will be extended to coincide with the software development tasks.

The impact assessments, based on the BIM models, will be documented in the WP5 deliverables, expected in November 2026, M42 of the project.

2. Development of the demo BIM models

Based on the **sketches** included in the project proposal, Societat Organica and VUB have coordinated the first design iterations for the demos in Sketchup (Barcelona, 3D) and AutoCad (Brussels, 2D). Both models were then consolidated in BIM to apply for the building permit.

In coordination with the WP3 partners, requirements are being established for the further development of these models, including the **technical data** to be integrated, the **BIM protocol** to be followed and the **Level of Detail** to be reached.

A first draft of the different models was made available on the project repository and delivered to the WP3 partners to test the prototype of the 6D-BIM modules.

2.1. The Barcelona demo

2.1.1. First design iterations

In Barcelona, the first design of the demo was drawn in **Sketchup** by Societat Organica. It helped the demo team reflect on the best **location** for the project on the site of the Santa Perpetua Castle, and was iterated to best demonstrate the Reconstruct **solutions**. Different designs were evaluated to make a final decision on the structure, the modularity and orientation of the façade elements and the way to reversibly connect them to each other.

Figure 1. The Sketchup model from the first design phase | Societat Organica,2023

2.1.2. The Architectural BIM Model

Developer: Societat Organica (SOO)

Platform of BIM model: ArchiCad

With most of the key design decisions established in Sketchup, a second architectural model was developed in BIM by Societat Organica. This model, with a more detailed design of the modular prefab elements and demountable connections, will be passed on to the architect in charge of the building permit application. He/she will then further develop the BIM model to guide the execution of the construction works.

Figure 3. The first version of the Archicad Model | Societat Orgánica, 2024

Figure 4. The Archicad floor plan and facades | Societat Orgánica, 2024

2.2. The Brussels demo

2.2.1. First design iterations

The demo team in Brussels worked in **2D AutoCad** to establish the first plans of their project. In its earliest version, the design was based on the initial sketches included in the project proposal.

Figure 5. The sketch of the Brussels demo for the project proposal | VUB, 2022

A first adaptation to the model was to expand the volume of the building and align it with the **programmatic requirements** established by Green Energy Park. As requested in their Project Brief, a meeting room for presentations will occupy the ground floor, while the first floor will be reserved for catering and expositions.

Then, a second round of adaptations were made to align the dimensions of the floor and façade elements with the **design grid of the Qbix building system**, developed by Holland Composites. Following the same logic, the final placement of the window openings and the distribution of the technical systems was determined. For the choice of façade materials, timber cladding was found to be the most demountable and low-carbon option in their **Qbix** catalogue (the others being glued brick slips, rendering and panel cladding).

Figure 6. Ground floor of the Brussels demo in CAD | VUB, 2023

Figure 7. First floor of the Brussels demo in CAD | VUB, 2023

2.2.2. The Production BIM Model

Developer: Holland Composites (HOL)

Platform: SolidWorks

In the case of the Brussels demo, a second model was developed by the manufacturer, Holland Composites, to prepare the production of the hybrid demo structure. The model is based on their **Qbix** catalogue of modular components and combines **steel elements** for the columns with **prefabricated Duplicor sandwich elements** for the floors and façades. Both are on a standardised 85 cm grid.

Two iterations of this Solidworks model were made by Holland Composites to inform decisions on massing, standardise window openings and choose materials. The model was exported and shared with Teesside University to start development of the 6D-BIM.

Figure 8. The First Iteration of the SolidWorks Model | Holland Composites, 2023

Figure 9. The Second Iteration of the SolidWorks Model | Holland Composites, 2024

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2.2.3. The Architectural BIM Model

Developer: SAN-CMU Architecten

Platform: AutoCad Revit

Figure 10. The Revit Model for the building permit | SAN-CMU Architecten, 2024

When **SAN-CMU Architecten** was appointed as the architect for the Brussels demo, a new model was drafted by the designers in AutoCad Revit, which is their standard practice. The plans resulting from this model were presented to the municipality in preparation for the **building permit** application and will be used next for the tendering and coordination of the **construction works**.

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Figure 11. Façades of the Brussels demo | SAN-CMU Architecten, 2024

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Figure 12. Building section of the Brussels demo | SAN-CMU Architecten, 2024

3. Conclusions

The **sequence of models**, presented in this report show that the value chain of the construction sector can still be very fragmented, with each stakeholder modelling new versions of the project on their own software platform. This lack of integration creates a lot of inefficiencies (compared to other sectors) but is, in part, inherent to the process. After all, the requirements for these models differ greatly depending on the stakeholder's objectives. Brainstorming about siting and massing, applying for a building permit or preparing the manufacturing of building elements are indeed very different things.

Although the demos are small, the process of building them still proves to be quite **representative for the complexity of the building process**. We look at this as an opportunity for the software developers in WP3 **to test the value of their digital tools for each of these stakeholders and purposes**.

This way, the demos are not only representative for different climates, functions, regulatory contexts and on- or offsite fabrication, they also challenge us to meet the requirements of the different stakeholders involved, in different phases of the process. In our upcoming **cocreation activities** with these stakeholders, we will gather insights on how to best adapt the Reconstruct solutions to each of their workflows, help them to efficiently meet their (circular) objectives and foster further integration.

To that end, VUB will establish a **focus group of local demo stakeholders**, selected from the clusters, to support the development of the tools and incorporate a **user perspective**. At the request of the partners and software developers, this focus group may offer input on **user needs**, preferences and pain points, provide **user stories and use cases** to guide the design and prioritise development decisions or **test prototypes** to identify issues and evaluate the user experience. Through **co-creation sessions**, the users will be invited to brainstorm and refine ideas with the development team and iterate features and solutions together.

These activities will be documented as a contribution to the **WP3 deliverables**, planned in May 2026.

